

Integration of data repositories into EOSC based on communities approaches

Introduction

The agriculture, food and environment research community faces many challenges common to all: Easily find and publish data, preserve them, and facilitate their treatment and analyse through computing solutions.

Examples of needs:

*"I need to integrate innovative services that allow researchers to **analyse data** and **publish it** easily. Our information system must guarantee long-term storage of experimental data"* - **Engineer, Phenome-Emphasis community**

*"I need an easy **access to the data produced on the experimental platforms**. I need to **correlate various datasets**. I need an easy access to publish curated datasets or models."* - **Research Engineer, Phenome-Emphasis community**

To address these needs, this use case aims to create a flexible federated research data ecosystem for the agrifood community through four aspects:

- ★ long term data preservation,
- ★ connecting data repositories,
- ★ virtual research environments,
- ★ cloud computing.

USE CASE

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COMMUNITIES

Earth science
Environmental science
Life science

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PARTNERS

Challenges addressed

- ★ Data findability and reusability
- ★ Data integration
- ★ Data processing
- ★ Reproducibility

Benefits through EOSC-Pillar

By using the **EOSC-Pillar Federated FAIR Data Space (F2DS)** data providers and repositories will be able to make their data findable, accessible, and reusable by the whole community within the context of EOSC. As a direct consequence, this task will enable and/or increase interoperability among the repositories. Furthermore, the use case will leverage EOSC data services such as B2SAFE in order to implement long-term preservation of the institutional data repositories.

With EOSC distribution, the agrifood community as a whole will gain access to a research environment on which to process, analyse and visualise data in-situ with appropriate compute infrastructure, without the need to download them first, fostering collaborations and cross-fertilisation.

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Highlights

What has been achieved

- ★ Widening the agrifood initial scope through collaboration with partners.
- ★ Deployment of a Virtual Research Environment in D4Science.
- ★ Deployment of OpenStack over INRAE's and France Grille's infrastructures.
- ★ Provisioning of Kubernetes Clusters based on INRAE's and France Grille's infrastructures.
- ★ Deployment of JupyterHub on INRAE's infrastructures.
- ★ Deployment of renku on INRAE 's infrastructures.
- ★ Deployment of binder on INRAE's infrastructures.
- ★ Mapping between CINES archiving tool (VITAM) and DataINRAE metadata.
- ★ Creation of Data INRAE openAPI definition for help integrating dataverse based repositories data in Federated FAIR Data Space (F2DS).

- ★ Development of a connector between dataverse based data repository and D4Science VRE.
- ★ Development of a connector between dataverse based data repository and JupyterHub.
- ★ Setup a connector between CINES archiving tool (VITAM) and Data INRAE for archiving automatically Data INRAE's data in VITAM.
- ★ Connection between INRAE jupyterHub and D4Science platform as a jupyter notebook provider.

Next steps

- ★ Developing a connector between dataverse and renku.
- ★ Developing a connector between dataverse and binder.
- ★ Setup interoperability between Fraunhofer Marketplace and F2DS.
- ★ Setup interoperability between Fraunhofer Marketplace and dataverse based repository.

